

EFFECTIVE PLACEMENT OF DATABASE FRAGMENTS IN INTERFAITH SYSTEMS

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Abstract. *The problem of optimal placement of distributed database fragments is one of the fundamental scientific and technical challenges in designing distributed information systems. This issue falls under the class of nonlinear programming, where during the initial design phase, the size of fragments and their access frequency are based only on approximate data. During the operational phase, these parameters are determined through reliable statistical evaluation. The dynamic operating mode of the system requires regular optimization of the placement schemes for distributed database fragments, which reduces network traffic and enhances overall efficiency. The components of the distributed information system are interconnected through a data transmission network and consist of local computing networks, local database servers, and routers. This approach ensures efficient utilization of resources.*

Keywords: *distributed database (DDB), fragment placement, replication, optimal placement, network traffic, local database (LDB), system efficiency, query processing, update costs, network throughput, mathematical models, network nodes, data transfer costs, efficient management.*

RELEVANCE.

Finding the optimal layout of distributed database fragments (DDB) is one of the most important tasks in the design of distributed information systems (DIS) for large corporations and enterprises. It is well known that many of these combinatorial problems still do not have exact solutions, since they belong to the class of nonlinear programming problems. When developing a DAT, many preliminary data (for example, the size of DDB fragments and the frequency of their mention) are available only as estimates. But during operation, this data is available for reliable statistical assessment. In addition, the DAT operating mode can change over time under the influence of various factors, so regular optimization of DDB fragment placement schemes allows you to reduce the load to a minimum, which is especially important for networks with intensive network traffic [1: 18].

Let us consider a network information system (DAT), in which the nodes $\{S_i; i = 1, N\}$ connected to trunk channels via a data transmission network (DN), having certain cost characteristics and technical parameters (bandwidth). One node contains:

- A router for connecting to the data transmission network.
- A local area network (LAN) connecting user worksDISions;
- A server with local database support (LMB);

METHOD

To cover the research topic, such methods as scientific description, comparative, mathematical modeling, cost minimization and component analysis were used.

MAIN PART

For all users of the network information system (NIS) under study, there is a single information space in the form of a distributed database (DDB), consisting of fragments $\{F_j; j = 1, M\}$. These fragments (individual arrays, tables, files, MB objects, etc.) are placed in a certain order on different servers [2:145].

A complete description of a specific deployment option for distributed database fragments (DDB) $X = \|x_{ij}, i = \overline{1, N}; j = \overline{1, M}\|$ is introduced the matrix. The elements of this matrix can take the following values:

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the fragment } F_j \text{ is current in local database in package } S_i; \\ 0, & \text{on the contrary.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Replication replicates database fragments (DBs), meaning that the same data can be stored in multiple local databases (LMBs). This provides users with convenient and fast local access to data [3:29]. Accordingly, any $j = 1, M$ for F_j The number of copies of the fragment is expressed by the following equation:

$$n_j = \sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

n_j - the total number of copies of the fragment F_j .

Each pair of nodes in the system S_i and S_j are assumed to be connected to each other via direct or multiplexed duplex channels. Thus, each node in the network has access to data from any other node. The cost of transmitting one unit of information in a communication between d_{ij} [4:877] is defined as:

$d_{ij} = d_{ji}$, that is, the transmission costs are symmetric;

$d_{ii} = 0$, that is, there is no cost for a node to transmit data to itself $d_{ii} = 0 (i = \overline{1, N})$.

Users of the information system (IS) under analysis are divided into separate groups, which belong to specific local area networks (LAN). These users create search queries to select the necessary information.

It is also assumed that during the processing of such a query, one of the fragments of the database (DB) will be addressed. Which fragment this address belongs to is defined by an index in the form of $(j = 1, M)$ and it determines the type of query.

Users S_i from the node $(i = 1, \dots, N)$ incoming j -type search queries with constant intensity is carried out at the level of λ_{ij} . If local database (LMB) S_i on the node F_j contains a fragment ($x_{ij} = 1$), these queries are internal queries and can be processed at their origin (in the LMB), without having to refer to other elements. If $x_{ij} = 0$, the survey becomes a remote survey, S_k is directed to the node, where $x_{kj} = 1$ condition must be met $k \neq i$.

Results obtained during the processing of remote search queries S_i and S_k . The data between the nodes is returned to the source node via transmission channels. As a result, the total data volume θ_{ij} is equal to [5:1726].

The problem of optimal placement of fragments of a distributed database (DDB). The efficiency of a distributed information system (DIS) and its performance indicators depend not only on the parameters of technical means (servers and communication channels), but also on the strategy of information placement. The replication process, which is the creation of data copies, allows to reduce the response time to search queries and increase the reliability of the system. However, as the number of replications increases, more memory is required to store data. The cost of synchronizing copies increases [6:18].

Thus, the number of copies (redundancy level) is a compromise between performance and resource requirements, taking into account many factors. In addition, for organizing effective search queries in DIS, optimal distribution of resources between nodes is important [7:6377]. This problem is considered a key one in optimizing the placement of DDB fragments.

Analysis of known models shows that the application of queuing theory requires mathematically complex equipment. Therefore, a more common approach in practice is a simpler method aimed at minimizing the volume of data transfer over computer network channels. This approach allows to increase the efficiency of the system by reducing data exchange during DIS operation. As the need for data transfer decreases, the speed of query processing increases [8:19].

If a copy of each DDB fragment is placed on each node, all search queries are processed locally, eliminating the need for data transfer over network links. However, when a file is updated, a data packet is sent to all nodes that have copies of this file. This increases the update cost. Therefore, from the point of view of update cost, storing only one copy of each fragment can improve the efficiency of the network. Based on this analysis, the problem of determining the optimal number of copies for each DDB fragment arises. The goal is to minimize the total cost of processing all queries. Based on the comprehensive approach of DIS optimization, it is appropriate to relate this issue to the optimal distribution of DDB fragments across network nodes [9:80].

Solution to the problem: if $x_{ij} = 0$ (that is, in the local database, on the node S_i , fragment F_j does not exist), then when j-type search requests are received from users on this node, the required data will have to be transmitted from another node. In this case, the requests will arrive at the same time, and the total amount of data transmitted will be as follows: $\lambda_{ij}\theta_{ij}$, here:

λ_{ij} - j-intensity of j-type requests;

θ_{ij} - the volume of data being transmitted.

The node where the copy of the file is located S_m assume that, in this case $x_{mj} = 1$ and $m \neq i$. This node provides the information needed for search queries. File storage node S_m is selected based on the following condition: $d_{im} = \min_{\text{here}} d_{ik}$; d_{ik} - nodes S_i and S_k the cost of transmission between; $k: x_{kj} = 1$, that the node F_j with the lowest cost is selected from the set of nodes that have a fragment [10:1254].

This mathematical expression helps to determine the location of the fragment for optimal data transmission in the network and minimize costs. As a result of the simultaneous operation of a distributed information system (DIS), the following total costs arise due to the exchange of information over network channels when processing search queries:

$$C_1(X) = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\sum_{j=1}^M \left[(1 - x_{ij}) \cdot (\lambda_{ij} \cdot \theta_{ij} \cdot \min(d_{ik})) \right] \right] \quad (3)$$

$$k: x_{kj} = 1.$$

Explanation of elements:

$C_1(X)$ -the total cost of processing requests on the network.

N -the number of nodes in the network.

M - Number of database fragments.

x_{ij} - indicator, if fragment F_j exists in the node S_i , $x_{ij} = 1$, otherwise $x_{ij} = 0$.

$(1 - x_{ij})$ - indicates that the fragment is not available, meaning that only the cost for remote requests is taken into account.

λ_{ij} - Request intensity (how often a request is sent from node i to fragment j).

θ_{ij} - The amount of information transmitted as a result of the request.

$\min d_{ik}$ - Minimum cost of transmission between nodes (from i to k, where the k-node contains the fragment).

This formula is used to calculate the total cost in DIS, where:

- Information not available locally is transmitted remotely;
- Costs are determined by the transmission intensity, the volume of data, and the transmission distance.

This approach helps to develop optimal strategies for improving the efficiency of DIS and minimizing costs. The costs associated with extension requests are as follows:

$$C_2(X) = \sum_{i=1}^N [\sum_{j=1}^M [\lambda'_{ij} \cdot \theta'_{ij} \cdot (\sum_{k=1}^N x_{kj} \cdot d_{ik})]] \quad (4)$$

$C_2(X)$ - represents the cost of updating and synchronizing fragments.

- λ'_{ij} - intensity of update requests.

θ'_{ij} - the amount of data transmitted in update requests.

x_{kj} - indicator, if fragment F_j exists in the node S_k , $x_{kj} = 1$, otherwise $x_{kj} = 0$.

d_{ik} - data transmission costs between nodes S_i and S_k .

$\sum_{k=1}^N x_{kj} d_{ik}$ - the sum of the transmission costs from all k-nodes to node i for fragment j.

To minimize update costs and improve network efficiency by optimally placing fragments.

$$C(X) = \sum_{i=1}^N [\sum_{j=1}^M [(1 - x_{ij}) \cdot \lambda_{ij} \cdot \theta_{ij} \cdot \min(d_{ik})] + \sum_{k=1}^N \lambda'_{ij} \cdot \theta'_{ij} \cdot x_{kj} \cdot d_{ik}] \quad (5)$$

$k: x_{kj} = 1$ This expression denotes an indexed condition, i.e., k - node S_k is being discussed, and this condition is expressed as follows: $x_{kj} = 1$: If fragment j exists at node k, based on constraints 1 and 2.

The technology of efficient deployment of distributed database fragments can be used in systems that require fast, reliable and efficient management of large volumes of data in any field. This approach is critical for a wide range of industries, including government, financial services, healthcare, education, trade, telecommunications, transportation, energy, defense and security. By quickly exchanging information between systems, efficiently using resources, reducing costs and increasing reliability, organizations can coordinate and optimize their activities. This, in turn, increases the overall efficiency of the organization and creates convenience for users.

CONCLUSION:

This study is devoted to the issue of efficient placement of distributed database fragments in interdepartmental religious systems and has important scientific and practical significance in the field of modern information and communication technologies. Distributed database (DDB) serves to improve interconnected activities by creating a single information space for large organizations, including religious bodies. The study provides a scientific basis for how to improve the efficiency of the system through the efficient deployment of DDB fragments. It is known that the placement of DDB fragments depends not only on the capabilities of technical means - servers and network channels, but also on how the fragments are placed. Large amounts of information are exchanged between religious authorities, so the important tasks are the efficient use of resources, reducing network traffic and ensuring fast access to information. To achieve these goals, effective methods of replication (creating copies of data) and their management were studied. The study, based on mathematical models and formulas, proposed methods for minimizing the costs of placing and updating DDB fragments. This allows for a balance between local and remote requests, determining where each request is processed. Also, by controlling the replication level, the

reliability of the system increases, taking into account the need to limit the number of redundant copies. The results of this study are of practical importance in the development of religious interdepartmental systems, due to which not only technical efficiency is achieved, but also the economic benefit of the system is ensured by saving time and resources. In conclusion, this article provides an important basis for reliable and fast information exchange between religious organizations through effective DDB management.

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